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**ПРАВИЛО АДДИТИВНОСТИ КАК ПРОГНОСТИЧЕСКИЙ ИНСТРУМЕНТ ДЛЯ
ВЕЛИЧИНЫ ЭНЕРГИИ ВЫСШЕЙ ЗАПОЛНЕННОЙ МОЛЕКУЛЯРНОЙ
ОРБИТАЛИ ОРГАНИЧЕСКОЙ МОЛЕКУЛЫ**

**ADDITIVITY RULE AS A PROGNOSTIC TOOL FOR ENERGY VALUE OF HIGHEST
OCCUPIED MOLECULAR ORBITAL (OR HOMO) OF ORGANIC MOLECULE**

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Аннотация: В этом обзоре рассматривается возможность расширенного применения правила аддитивности, а именно для теоретического расчета значения энергии высшей заполненной молекулярной орбитали. Автором получены и проверены данные справочного характера для основных функциональных групп органических соединений на примере органических производных фосфина (с помощью квантовохимического программного пакета PCGAMESS2009) как для соединений, имеющих склонность к сопряжению, так и не имеющих таковой.

Ключевые слова: граничные орбитали, энергия, ВЗМО, правило аддитивности, органические производные, мезомерный эффект, GAMESS, Ab Initio, Chemission, ChemOffice

Abstract: In this review, we consider the possibility of an extended application of the additivity rule, namely, for a theoretical calculation of the energy of a higher filled molecular orbital. The author obtained and checked the reference data for the main functional groups of organic compounds using the example of organic derivatives of phosphine (using the PCGAMESS2009 quantum chemical software package) both for compounds that are prone to and do not have conjugation.

Keywords: boundary orbitals, energy, HOMO, additivity rule, organic derivatives, mesomeric effect, GAMESS, Ab Initio, Chemissian, ChemOffice

Introduction

Mathematically strictly additive are only the masses of the bodies being mixed, but sometimes additive volumes, as well as molecular masses.

Boundary orbitals, including the highest filled molecular orbital, are intended to predict the reactivity of compounds.

In radicals or excited molecules, the role of one of these orbitals or both can be played by singly occupied molecular orbitals, the most important characteristic is their partial electron density, i.e. density on individual atoms (boundary electron density or reactivity index).

The reactions most readily occur in the case of maximum overlap of the boundary molecular orbitals.

Overlapping leads to charge transfer from the highest occupied orbitals of the donor to the lowest free orbital of acceptor [1-14].

Experiment Procedure

The choice of organic molecules. Steps of scientific research.

Organic derivatives of phosphine were used for the experiment. For the first stage of the study, this determination of the value of the HOMO energy of the main functional groups,

organic molecules (OM), which are derivatives of phosphine $(\text{H}_2\text{P} - \underset{\text{H}_2}{\text{C}} -)_{\text{val}}^{\text{FG}}$ and $(\text{H}_2\text{P} -)_{\text{val}}^{\text{FG}}$, where FG is a functional group having a valence from 1 to *val*. Conducting the

second stage: as a test of the additivity rule, the structure of composition

and $\begin{array}{c} \text{FG}_2 \\ | \\ \text{FG}_1 - \text{P} - \text{FG}_3 \end{array}$. Functional groups were selected by their ability to manifest +M (donor functional groups) or -M (acceptor functional groups) by the principle of successive alternation of them in the molecule.

Quantum-chemical calculation technology

Quantum-chemical calculation (numerical experiment) was carried out in the program GAMESS-2009, by means of visualization tools of input structure of CambridgeSoft 2013 software package and output data on the boundary orbitals of the Chemissian 4.33 program. OM were preliminarily optimized with a) MM+, b) Ab Initio HF/MINI*. The actual calculation was carried out by the Ab Initio MP2/DZV*.

As a simplification, since phosphine is a donor molecule, it was assumed that $E(\text{HOMO})_{\text{P}} = E(\text{HOMO})_{\text{-PH}_2} = E(\text{HOMO})_{\text{-PH}_2} = E(\text{HOMO})_{\text{PH}_3}$ and $E(\text{HOMO})_{\text{-CH}_3} = \text{const} = 0,634$, which was calculated on the basis of methylphosphine.

Results and discussion

Step 1

The energy of HOMO phosphine molecule PH₃ is -10.482 eV, which the author takes as an inorganic prototype (I). Table 1 lists the HOMO energies of the most common functional groups in the $(\text{H}_2\text{P}-\text{C}-)_{\text{val}}^{\text{FG}}$:

Table 1. The energies of HOMO of common FG

Functional group	Energy contribution to E (HOMO _{OM}), eV	Functional group	Energy contribution to E (HOMO _{OM}), eV
-O-	0,452	-OH	0,433
-Cl	-0,051	-COOH	0,044
Secondary carbon atom ¹	0,068	-CN	-0,354
-NH-	-0,095	-S-	0,615
-C≡C-	-0,019	-CH=CH ₂	0,710
-SO ₃ H	-0,378	-C ₆ H ₅	1,585
-NH ₂	0,531	-NH-N=O	-0,021
-CH=O	-0,032	-CO-	0,234
-N-	-0,481	-P-	-0,389
/		/	

This table is of value as reference data.

Step 2.

The second step of calculations is checking the additivity rule with a formula derived empirically by the author:

$${}^t E(\text{HOMO})_{\text{OM}} = {}^I E(\text{HOMO}) + \{ {}^{\text{OM}} E(\text{HOMO})_{\text{FG}_1} + \dots + {}^{\text{OM}} E(\text{HOMO})_{\text{FG}_n} + {}^{\text{OM}} E(\text{HOMO})_{\text{C}} \}$$

где ${}^I E(\text{HOMO})$ is E (HOMO) of "inorganic prototype" I (in the article this is PH₃) ${}^{\text{OM}} E(\text{HOMO})_{\text{FG}_n}$ is E (HOMO) of functional group in OM ${}^{\text{OM}} E(\text{HOMO})_{\text{C}}$ is E (HOMO) of "central fragment" C (in the article this is a tertiary phosphorus atom) generated by I

The results of calculations for this formula are presented in Table 3 for OM

according to the reference data taken from Table 1

¹ is meant -CH₂-, for the calculation of which was used

; the methylene :CH₂ contributes to

HOMO_{OM} equal to 0,604 eV

Table 2. Information on verification of the additivity rule for nonconjugate molecules

No. of OM	symbol of FG	FG name	Energy value of HOMO _{OM} , eV		k, Theoretical / Practical
			Practical ²	Theoretical	
1	FG ₁ FG ₂ FG ₃	-CH ₃ -NH ₂ -Cl	-9,434	-9,553	1,013
2	FG ₁ FG ₂ FG ₃	-COOH -SO ₃ H -CH=CH ₂	-10,210	-10,291	1,008
3	FG ₁ FG ₂ FG ₃	-COOH -NH ₂ -CH=CH ₂	-9,448	-9,382	0,993
4	FG ₁ FG ₂ FG ₃	-CH ₃ -COOH -Cl	-9,845	-10,040	1,020

It can be seen that the difference between the theoretically and practically calculated energy values exceeds 0.1 only in the case of 2 donor and 1 acceptor substituents. The most reliable derivation of the formula with a conversion factor k.

In OM, where the substituents are similar in properties (all donor or all acceptor), the coefficient may be taken as 1.01.

In OM, where the substituents are different in properties, the coefficient may be taken as 1.006, although in this case the set value of the coefficient is less reliable.

The results of calculations for this formula are presented in Table 3 for $\text{FG}_1 - \overset{\text{FG}_2}{\underset{|}{\text{P}}} - \text{FG}_3$, where there is conjugation or a significant reduction in the strength of the P-FG bond, according to the reference data taken from Table 1

Table 3. Information on the verification of the additivity rule for molecules exhibiting conjugation or a significant decrease in the strength of the P—FG bond

No. of OM	symbol of FG	FG name	Energy value of HOMO _{OM} , eV		k, Theoretical / Practical
			Practical	Theoretical	
1	FG ₁ FG ₂ FG ₃	-CH ₃ -NH ₂ -Cl	-10,006	-9,553	0,955
2	FG ₁ FG ₂ FG ₃	-COOH -SO ₃ H -CH=CH ₂	-11,173	-10,291	0,921
3	FG ₁ FG ₂ FG ₃	-COOH -NH ₂ -CH=CH ₂	-9,565	-9,382	0,981
4	FG ₁ FG ₂ FG ₃	-CH ₃ -COOH -Cl	-10,370	-10,040	0,968

² This refers to the calculation made in GAMESS-2009. Theoretical is a calculation made according to the additivity rule

The difference between theoretically and practically calculated energy values exceeds 0.4 only in the case of OM having acceptor substituents, and very close to 1 eV.

In OM 1, 3, 4, the coefficient k on the average is 0.97.

In OM, where all the substituents are acceptor, the coefficient is the averaged value of 0.9.

In non-conjugated compounds in general, E (HOMO) is less.

Thus, the connection between the two methods of calculating the energy of the highest filled molecular orbitals (practical **pr**: using PCGAMESS2009 and theoretical **t**: according to additivity rule) is:

$$\frac{t}{k} E(\text{HOMO}) = \text{pr} E(\text{HOMO})$$

Conclusion

It is known that the rule of additivity of covalent bonds is valid only for non-conjugated bonds [1-14]. When conjugated, the lengths of bonds strongly deviate from the standard values; double bonds are extended, and simple bonds between them are shortened.

The correctness of the author's deduction of reference data, despite some assumptions (the coarsest of which is $E(\text{HOMO})_{-P} = E(\text{HOMO})_{-PH} = E(\text{HOMO})_{-PH_2} = E(\text{HOMO})_{PH_3}$), is confirmed by a rather small difference theoretically calculated values from practically. The additivity rule as a tool for predicting the numerical value of the energy of a higher filled molecular orbital can be used in the case of nonconjugate and conjugated compounds to within 0.1. In this case, the data of Table 1 can claim universality in the case when it is necessary to calculate the energy of the highest filled molecular orbital for organic molecules derived from an inorganic low-molecular compound (ethers, amines, etc.). It is very likely that the foregoing applies to the value of the energy of the lowest vacant molecular orbital, as well as for molecules that do not have a related inorganic low molecular weight compound that is genetically related to them.

References

1. Şen, N , YÜKSEL, B . (2016). Theoretical studies on the thermodynamic properties and detonation properties of cyclotrimethylene trinitramine (RDX) with aluminum and boron metals.. Journal of the Turkish Chemical Society, Section A: Chemistry, 3 (3), 657-668. DOI: 10.18596/jotcsa.287301
2. Tanya M. S. David, Cheng Zhang, and Sam-Shajing Sun, "Development of Low Energy Gap and Fully Regioregular Polythienylenevinylene Derivative," Journal of Chemistry, vol. 2014, Article ID 379372, 7 pages, 2014. doi:10.1155/2014/379372
3. ÖZDEMİR, T , GÖKÇE, H . (2017). Experimental and Theoretical Investigations of Molecular Structure and Vibrational Frequencies of Hypericin Molecule. Cumhuriyet Science Journal, 38 (4), 759-769. DOI: 10.17776/csj.340497
4. Nonnenmacher, M.; Buck, D. M.; Kunz, D. *Beilstein J. Org. Chem.* **2016**, *12*, 1884–1896. doi:10.3762/bjoc.12.178
5. Ghosh, D.C.; Bhattacharyya, S. Molecular Orbital and Density Functional Study of the Formation, Charge Transfer, Bonding and the Conformational Isomerism of the Boron Trifluoride (BF₃) and Ammonia (NH₃) Donor-Acceptor Complex. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* **2004**, *5*, 239-264. doi:10.3390/i5050239
6. Apoorva Dwivedi, Vikas Baboo, and Abhishek Bajpai, "Fukui Function Analysis and Optical, Electronic, and Vibrational Properties of Tetrahydrofuran and Its Derivatives: A Complete Quantum Chemical Study," Journal of Theoretical Chemistry, vol. 2015, Article ID 345234, 11 pages, 2015. doi:10.1155/2015/345234

7. Sławiński, J.; Żołnowska, B.; Brzozowski, Z.; Kawiak, A.; Belka, M.; Bączek, T. Synthesis and QSAR Study of Novel 6-Chloro-3-(2-Arylmethylene-1-methylhydrazino)-1,4,2-benzodithiazine 1,1-Dioxide Derivatives with Anticancer Activity. *Molecules* **2015**, *20*, 5754-5770. doi:[10.3390/molecules20045754](https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules20045754)
8. Hong Ju, Li Ding, Can Sun, and Jie-jing Chen, "Quantum Chemical Study on the Corrosion Inhibition of Some Oxadiazoles," *Advances in Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 2015, Article ID 519606, 5 pages, 2015. doi: 10.1155/2015/519606
9. Nwankwo, H.U.; Ateba, C.N.; Olasunkanmi, L.O.; Adegunle, A.S.; Isabirye, D.A.; Onwudiwe, D.C.; Ebenso, E.E. Synthesis, Characterization, Antimicrobial Studies and Corrosion Inhibition Potential of 1,8-dimethyl-1,3,6,8,10,13-hexaazacyclotetradecane: Experimental and Quantum Chemical Studies. *Materials* **2016**, *9*, 107. doi:[10.3390/ma9020107](https://doi.org/10.3390/ma9020107)
10. Govindarajan, M.; Abdelhameed, A.S.; Al-Saadi, A.A.; Attia, M.I. Experimental and Theoretical Studies of the Vibrational and Electronic Properties of (2E)-2-[3-(1H-imidazol-1-yl)-1-phenyl-propylidene]-N-phenylhydrazinecarboxamide: An Anticonvulsant Agent. *Appl. Sci.* **2015**, *5*, 955-972. doi:[10.3390/app5040955](https://doi.org/10.3390/app5040955)
11. K. Laarej, M. Bouachrine, S. Radi, S. Kertit, and B. Hammouti, "Quantum Chemical Studies on the Inhibiting Effect of Bipyrazoles on Steel Corrosion in HCl," *E-Journal of Chemistry*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 419-424, 2010. doi:10.1155/2010/273206
12. I. O. Arukalam, I. O. Madu, N. T. Ijomah, C. M. Ewulonu, and G. N. Onyeagoro, "Acid Corrosion Inhibition and Adsorption Behaviour of Ethyl Hydroxyethyl Cellulose on Mild Steel Corrosion," *Journal of Materials*, vol. 2014, Article ID 101709, 11 pages, 2014. doi:10.1155/2014/101709
13. Denisova, A.V.; Tibbelin, J.; Emanuelsson, R.; Ottosson, H. A Computational Investigation of the Substituent Effects on Geometric, Electronic, and Optical Properties of Siloles and 1,4-Disilacyclohexa-2,5-dienes. *Molecules* **2017**, *22*, 370. doi:[10.3390/molecules22030370](https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules22030370)
14. Peng Shang and Lei Zhang, "Preparation and Electronic Property Investigation of Zinc(II)-Schiff Base Complexes in the Confined Space," *Journal of Chemistry*, vol. 2013, Article ID 206847, 6 pages, 2013. doi:10.1155/2013/206847